

Future Crash Configurations: Analysis of the Impact of Future Vehicles in Mixed Traffic

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Abstract. Within the EU-funded SALIENT project (<https://www.salient-project.eu>), an analysis of crash configurations of new and future vehicle fleets (including heavier SUV-type vehicles and autonomous vehicles) has been developed. The future crash scenarios identified will be translated into relevant scenarios for further simulations and crash tests. The work laid out in this paper contains the results of a detailed literature and state-of-the-art review and a data analysis of relevant international datasets, to then propose considerations for future crash configurations and scenarios. These considerations explore in detail real-world data of crashes involving CCAM and automated vehicles. The results of this research aim to serve as a basis for a safe transition from today's user-driven vehicles to SAVs (semi-autonomous vehicles) and AVs (autonomous vehicles) in mixed traffic, to maximise compatibility between vehicles.

1 Introduction

The characteristics of privately owned cars are changing rapidly: not only are new models larger (1), but also heavier and with time (2), they are also equipped more frequently with higher levels of Advanced Driving Assistance Systems (ADAS) (3), which automate and connect the vehicles. This change needs to be reflected in the considerations of safety research for private vehicles, especially the considerations for collision constellations and crash scenarios in an updated vehicle traffic mix. This paper aims at introducing different factors, which may influence future crash scenarios and gives recommendations for safety designs of vehicles for car manufacturers, Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), crash test houses and governments.

This piece of research is part of the SALIENT project (4), which seeks in designing and validating a new design for the Front-End Structures (FES) of cars to future-proof them by creating an alternative which is safer, lightweight, circular, smart and can predict and counter-act on crashes before they happen.

2 Methods

In order to ensure a detailed analysis of the state of the art and future projection of vehicle fleets, a plethora of sources were consulted and analysed. The following

approach was applied to abstract the most common crash scenarios between Autonomous Vehicles (AV, with advanced ADAS systems) and Sport Activity Vehicles (SAV, representing the trend towards larger and heavier cars). The following methodology has been followed to gather insight and data on both vehicle types in sufficient number and detail:

1. Review of pre-existing and on-going research & development projects (namely OSCCAR (5) and SAFE-UP (6));
2. Review of existing and open databases of mixed traffic accidents (namely the California Department of Motor Vehicles (DMV) collision reports, USA (7), STATS19, UK (8), RAIDS, UK (9), iGLAD, SE (10), GIDAS, GER (11), VOIESUR, FR (12));
3. Filtering, cleaning, sorting and exploitation of data in terms for passenger safety of AVs;
4. Study of influence of environmental impacts (namely vehicle weight, electrification of fleets).

3 OSCCAR and SAFE-UP projects

This paper builds on two pre-existing EU-funded projects. Before presenting the most important findings of these projects on the current paper, it is important to also highlight their limitations, which was complimented by the further analysis. Both projects used data stemming from both real-world datasets and simulations, which is based on the assumption of linear impact velocities. Only a limited number of datasets are openly available, and the data is complex and difficult to interpret, larger datasets over longer periods will be required. Sophisticated filters were needed to create simulations which include abstracted data such as crash angles or overlaps. The datasets varied considerably between countries, which led to differences of up to 26% in the accuracy of results, demonstrating a high heterogeneity of data.

OSCCAR identified gaps of the existing accident scenario catalogue, with a focus on the gradual introduction of ADAS and AV into the average vehicle fleet mix on motorways, urban and rural roads. A market penetration of SAVs was estimated at 3% by 2025 and 66% by 2050, which is one of the baselines applied to our analysis. The project demonstrated that the number of crashes can be reduced, although the frequency of crashes at intersections (which ADAS systems are particularly unfit for) increased from 42% to 57%.

SAFE-UP analysed real-world data of car-to-car, car-to-Heavy Goods Vehicle (HGV) and car-to-Vulnerable Road User (VRU) encounters. HGV with a total weight ≥ 3.5 tons are disproportionately often involved in heads-on crashes in urban settings. Several different configurations can be adopted from the project findings, especially those involving a mix of light and heavy vehicle cases.

4 Databases and data analysis

National databases were also consulted, although many of them were excluded due to a lack of accuracy in the data collected, a statistically insignificant number of data entries or lack of documentation of the parameters per crash. The most accurate and therefore valuable to the data analyses is the openly available data of the DMV in California, US and the National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (NHTSA). This data has been extrapolated from the rest of the available data to create artificial samples applied to other datasets. In particular, two European databases: one of the City of Madrid, Spain (13) and one provided by the French Road Safety Observatory (OINSR) and extracted from the BAAC (French Government) (14).

US American databases are more comprehensive in the detail of accident characteristics and environmental conditions. A low level of stringency in selection criteria is applied due to the lack of uniformity in the different databases. Accidents with two vehicles and autonomous functionalities are considered, whether these features are in operation when the accident occurs. In addition, a study of accidents with contextual data is conducted. In previous studies, the data considered was referenced to the relative velocity, which is related to the severity of the accident. This could be useful if relevant data, such as yaw angle, were available, but it must be analysed correctly since the collision point is not enough to obtain the necessary data for the correct simulation of the accidents. Collisions with two moving vehicles require both angles from the different vehicles as different reference systems, which cannot be obtained in all the datasets.

4.1 Front-end AV collisions

In the first analysis of the collisions shows the areas affected by impacts in relation to the frequency in the filtered DMV dataset. AVs have a higher impact rate on the right-hand side than other vehicles when in motion. However, in stationary state, the front of the car shows a more even distribution of damage. This incompatibility between the vehicles could be the source of human error.

Table 1. Statistical weights for front-end involved impacts in AVs in mixed traffic, DNV database.

Crash with	AV in movement ($n = 339$)		Opponent in movement ($n = 302$)		General	
	$\frac{x}{n}$	x	$\frac{x}{n}$	x	$\frac{x}{n}$	x
AV stopped	-	-	0.00728	22	0.9145	310
Opponent stopped	0.05	17	-	-	0.8377	253
General	0.0855	29	0.1623	49	-	-

Further analysis into the behaviour of front-end damage in specific cases where vehicles collided with stationary vehicles was conducted. It is remarkable that there is a

difference in the damage to the front-end of the various vehicles. The relative weights for frontal collisions in the DMV Database are shown in **Table 1**. The data shows a tendency for AVs to receive more collisions while stationary in traffic (91.45%) than in the case of a non-AVs (83.77%). AVs in motion account for 5% of the collisions with stationary vehicles, with AVs being hit by other moving vehicles 7.28% of the time for head-on collisions in this selection of cases. Most of the damage is concentrated around the front passenger and the right side of the car. This shows that they may also be caused by human error and poor adaptation of humans to driving dynamics of AVs. The distribution of available data for each set also shows the comparison between datasets. The data handled by the different databases are of mixed traffic, but not all of them contain information about the level of autonomy of the AVs.

5 Results and discussion

The safety benefits of a new FES are clear; however, despite the availability of international standards and consumer tests, the current fleet of vehicles often fails to meet real-life accident issues. By establishing legal requirements, governments can ensure that no matter what the manufacturer's design goals are, a minimum level of safety is always provided. Safety conditions considering a new and lighter FES with respect to existing production cars, involves the considerations of car manufacturers, current legislations, tested for existing FES, consumer testing and specific needs of current vehicles. Therefore, a coherent plan for the future of vehicle safety will be needed that combines consumer testing, appropriate regulation, and new technology developments.

The crash scenarios considered in this paper are mainly rear impact, side impact, and frontal impact. Within the rear impact category, the motorway rear end and inner-city rear end will be studied further within the SALIENT project. For frontal impact, the analysis will cover both frontal crashes and head-on collisions in terms of energy absorption, deformation control, and intrusion protection. The results of the simulations will be used to develop new FES designs that can meet the safety performance requirements for the different crash scenarios, identify potential areas of improvement, and develop new designs that can meet the safety performance requirements for the different crash scenarios. The following scenarios are of great importance when it comes to the validation of FES systems:

- Legal ECE-R94-43, R-100 (offset, 40% overlap deformable barrier at a speed of 56 km/h);
- Legal UN R137 (full frontal rigid barrier, 50 km/h);
- EuroNCAP (consumer testing scenarios);
- Additional scenarios that test improved compatibility (e.g., different weight, different height of bumper);
- MPDB with increased weight (IIHS side impact or equivalent) and height;

According to literature, the prospective studies performed in OSCCAR and SAFE-UP should be considered. The following scenarios appear as relevant - all three of them should be explored during all of the following technical SALIENT WPs, from design conceptualisation, simulation design and crash test evaluation:

Table 2. Selected crash scenarios in mixed traffic settings.

Impact area	Impact reason	Research focus
Rear	Unexpected breaking of AV, causing a rear collision into the AV on motorways, inner-city and intersection settings	1) AIS1-2 injuries of AV occupants/passengers 2) Criticality for occupant/passengers of AV
Side	Collision at turning point of intersection	Criticality for occupant/passenger safety on-board of both vehicles
Front	1) Failed detection of object in front of AV 2) Human error of vehicle in on-coming traffic (e.g., wrong way drivers)	Criticality for occupant/passenger safety on-board of AV

In addition to the crash scenarios mentioned in the previous sections, SALIENT will also consider the following crash scenarios:

- Rigid barrier with full overlap at a speed of 56 km/h;
- Offset, 40% overlap deformable barrier at a speed of 56 km/h;
- Mobile Progressive Deformable Barrier (MPDB), increased weight and height;
- Mobile Progressive Deformable Barrier (MPDB) at different angles ($\sim 0\text{-}30^\circ$), impact points 0-60% overlap;
- Stationary barriers and adjusted speeds (reduced relative velocities compared to ECE and current Euro NCAP test protocols);
- Combination of compatibility testing and crash angle/ velocity;
- Crash avoidance scenarios (e.g., swerving to avoid a pedestrian, cyclist, vehicle).

6 Conclusions

This research draws key conclusions from consulting all available sources regarding collisions in mixed traffic from 2000-2017. This analysis provides a basis for the further development of a safety solutions for the current context and adapted to mixed traffic scenarios while meeting the requirements of circular economy, eco-design, and environmental friendliness. The results obtained through the analysis of different databases show that rear-end collisions are more frequent depending on weight and angle, which demonstrates the need to consider the different weights of light and heavy vehicles to increase crash compatibility. It can be observed that simulations map the ability of standardised active safety systems to mitigate crashes by 26-27% (11). However, when the same approach was used by the SAFE-UP project on the same database, different results for rear-end collisions between heavy goods vehicles and light passenger cars emerged, suggesting additional countermeasures for light-weight vehicles.

The research feeds the understanding of the context of mixed traffic which are relevant in the evaluation of safety solutions, in the design of restraint systems, in the study of the dynamic behaviour of autonomous and electric vehicles in collisions and as a basis for a better understanding of the effects of their uptake in the context of mixed traffic. Moreover, this research lays the foundations for the SALIENT project to design

a FES that considers all aspects and taking into account contextual data. The results serve as a basis for a transition from user-driven vehicles to SAVs and AVs in mixed traffic, to maximise compatibility between vehicles to minimise human injuries in accidents.

7 Declarations

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